

THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY ON PRICING IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *The relevance of the article is due to the growing importance of sustainable development and environmental responsibility in the global economy. Environmental policies, including carbon taxation, emission quotas and investments in clean technologies, significantly affect production costs and, as a result, pricing. Thus, the study of the impact of environmental policy on pricing is key to the formation of sustainable development strategies in this industry.*

Keywords: *oil and gas industry, environmental policy, pricing.*

INTRODUCTION

Environmental policy is becoming an increasingly important aspect of the modern world economy, including in the oil and gas industry, which plays a key role in the global economy. Given climate change, depletion of natural resources and growing interest in sustainable development, states and international organizations are taking measures to limit the negative impact of hydrocarbon production and use on the environment. As a result, oil and gas companies are facing new challenges related to compliance with environmental standards, which in turn affects their pricing strategies and financial results.

In the context of global environmental challenges such as climate change and environmental pollution, environmental policy is becoming a key element of the economic strategy of countries. The oil and gas industry, which is the main source of energy and a significant contribution to the GDP of many countries, is forced to adapt to new requirements, which makes the study of the impact of environmental policy on pricing in this area particularly relevant.

The choice of this topic is determined by several factors. Firstly, the oil and gas industry plays a key role in the global economy and makes a significant contribution to energy security. At the same time, its activities are accompanied by significant negative consequences for the environment. Secondly, with the growth of public awareness regarding environmental issues and increasing demands for sustainable development, companies are forced to reconsider their strategies and implement new technologies, which, in turn, affects the costs and prices of energy resources.

In addition, carbon taxes, emission quotas, and other environmental regulations imposed by governments affect companies' cost structures and financial performance. Increased costs of environmental compliance can lead to higher oil and gas prices, which affects both producers and end consumers.

METHODS

This article uses statistical and factor analysis techniques to quantify data and identify trends and patterns in environmental policymaking. Factor analysis, in turn, helps to identify hidden variables that influence pricing in the oil and gas industry and to group related factors to simplify the interpretation of results.

RESULTS

To begin with, it is advisable to consider two main objects of study in this article - environmental policy and pricing in the oil and gas industry. As noted earlier, environmental policy is a set of goals and principles established by an organization or state to improve the environmental aspects of its activities. Its goal is to ensure harmonious and sustainable development, in which nature, society and the economy interact in a balanced manner.

Key objectives of environmental policy:

conservation of natural resources: development and implementation of measures for the rational use and protection of natural resources;

reduction of negative impact: minimization of pollutant emissions and reduction of environmental risks;

development of environmentally friendly technologies: support for innovation and transition to sustainable production processes;

increasing environmental responsibility: formation of a culture of conscious attitude towards the environment in society;

environmental monitoring and control: ensuring an effective system for observing the state of nature and responding to environmental threats;

international cooperation: participation in global initiatives for nature conservation and fulfillment of environmental obligations. [1]

Many countries have adopted international agreements, such as the Paris Agreement, that require countries to reduce emissions and move toward sustainable use of natural resources. In response, many countries have introduced mandatory standards for the energy sector that require emissions to be minimized and energy efficiency to be increased. Companies are forced to invest heavily in upgrading equipment, installing emission control systems, and implementing cleaner technologies. All of this increases the cost of producing and refining oil and gas, which ultimately affects the price to the end consumer. For example, installing carbon capture and storage technologies, which are becoming more common, requires large capital investments and maintenance. These costs are passed on to consumers as companies seek to maintain their profits by increasing the price of their products.

Pricing in the oil and gas industry is a complex process that depends on many factors and includes economic, political, technological and environmental aspects. The main elements influencing the formation of oil and gas prices are production costs, transportation costs, global market conditions and government regulation.

One of the key factors is the balance of supply and demand on the global market. Growing global demand for energy resources, especially in developing countries, leads to higher prices. On the other hand, overproduction caused by the development of production technologies, such as shale oil, can lead to lower prices. Global economic crises, political instability in exporting countries and force majeure circumstances, such as pandemics or natural disasters, also play an important role.[2]

Let's look at environmental policy factors that influence pricing in the oil and gas industry.

Environmental policy has a significant impact on the oil and gas industry, including through carbon taxation. The introduction of carbon taxes encourages companies to revise their production processes to minimize emissions and reduce tax costs. However, for high-emissions of oil and gas companies, this represents a significant additional cost, forcing them to raise prices for

their products. In countries with carbon taxes, oil and gas companies factor these costs into their oil and gas prices, which can make energy resources more expensive.

In addition, sustainability standards such as ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) are gaining influence. Many investment funds and banks are limiting or stopping financing high-carbon projects, reducing the availability of capital for oil and gas companies. This forces them to seek alternative sources of financing or raise investment rates and meet sustainability standards to remain competitive.

Environmental policies also encourage the development of alternative energy sources such as solar and wind power through subsidies and tax breaks, which reduces demand for oil and gas. Countries in Europe and North America are implementing hydrocarbon phase-out programs, which reduces market demand for traditional energy sources and puts pressure on prices. Oil and gas companies must adapt to these changes, which leads to a decrease in their market share.

From a long-term perspective, despite the additional costs, oil and gas companies can take advantage of opportunities to innovate and invest in renewable energy. For example, companies like Shell and BP are already diversifying their revenues and reducing their reliance on hydrocarbons, which helps them remain competitive. [8]

Additionally, environmental policy includes restrictions on oil and gas production and processing to minimize environmental damage. This includes a ban on developing fields in nature conservation areas and strict standards for pollutant emissions. Companies must implement high environmental standards, which increases production and processing costs and increases the cost of production. Restrictions on exploration of new fields reduce the volume of supply on the market, which creates new conditions for the industry, pushing it towards more sustainable development.

An important component is also the cost of restoring the environment after accidents and spills. Large oil spills require expensive cleanup operations and ecosystem restoration. The costs of eliminating the consequences can reach billions of dollars and include the creation of environmental funds and compensation for damage to local communities. These costs increase the financial burden on companies and affect market prices.

Next, we will consider an analysis of the impact of environmental policy on pricing in the oil and gas industry. Between 2020 and 2023, gas, oil and carbon prices showed significant fluctuations, reflecting the influence of both global factors and EU environmental policy (table 1).

Table 1. Gas and oil pricing and carbon quota dynamics (ETS) in 2020–2023.

Period	Average gas price (EU), \$/1000 M ³	Gas price change in %	Brent oil price, \$/barrel	Oil price change in %	Carbon offset rate (ETS), €/t CO ₂
2020	132,7	161,8	51,8	80,9	24
2021	450,66	339,6	77,78	150,2	53
2022	1272	282,3	85,91	110,5	85
2023	502,3	39,5	77,04	89,7	90

Source: [4]

In 2020, gas and oil prices were low due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused a drop in demand. Carbon quotas were at €24 per tonne of CO₂, without having a significant impact on the market. In 2021, as the economy began to recover, gas prices increased by 339.6% and oil prices by 150.2%. This was accompanied by an increase in carbon quotas to €53, which increased

the cost of fossil fuels. In 2022, gas prices reached a record \$1,272 per 1,000 m³, and oil prices reached US\$85.91 per barrel, which was due to the energy crisis in Europe and the reduction in Russian gas supplies. Carbon quotas continued to rise to €85, supporting the transition to renewable energy.

In 2023, gas prices fell by 39.5%, amounting to US\$502.3 per 1,000 m³, thanks to increased LNG supplies and the growing share of renewable energy sources. The oil price remained stable, but fell to US\$77.04 per barrel. Carbon quotas rose to €90, continuing to stimulate decarbonization efforts. The gas price showed significant fluctuations, caused by both environmental initiatives (transition to renewable energy sources) and external factors (sanctions against Russia). Oil has been less affected by environmental policies in the short term, but increasing transport electrification and the rise of hydrogen pose long-term risks to oil demand.

CONCLUSION

Environmental policy has a significant impact on pricing in the oil and gas industry, as can be seen from the changes in gas and oil prices between 2020 and 2023. Carbon taxation, CO₂ emission quotas and the transition to renewable energy sources (RES) have increased costs for oil and gas companies, which is reflected in the final prices for consumers. Environmental requirements are becoming stricter, which forces companies to invest in modernization and compliance with new standards, increasing the cost of hydrocarbon production and processing.

A key factor is the carbon credits (ETS), which have become significantly more expensive over the period under review. In 2020, their price was €24 per tonne of CO₂, but by 2023 it had risen to €90, which has led to an increase in the cost of energy resources.

Environmental policies also promote the transition to clean energy sources, which reduces demand for hydrocarbons and creates long-term risks for the oil and gas sector. Companies such as Shell and BP are already diversifying their revenues by investing in renewable energy, which helps them remain competitive.

Thus, environmental policy and the transition to a low-carbon economy, in the short term, increase the growth of costs and carbon quotas, and increase the prices of fossil fuels. In the long term, the industry will be forced to adapt, switching to more environmentally friendly technologies and reducing dependence on hydrocarbons.

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